

CURRENT SIGNIFICANCE OF THE RULE OF LAW IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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The rule of law enshrined in our Constitution The principle of human rights and freedoms in our society to ensure the effective implementation of all reforms is an important guarantee of increase.

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Annotation: *The purpose of this article is to provide information on various measures aimed at ensuring the rule of law in our country, as well as which government agencies are involved in the implementation of the rule of law, and how these changes serve the interests of our people.*

Keywords: *Surat an-Nahl, “On Courts”, “Liberalization of Criminal Punishments”, “Habeas Corpus”, Judicial Investigation, “On the Supreme Council of Judges of the Republic of Uzbekistan” Court of Appeal, regional courts.*

The role of the Constitution in the formation of any state is invaluable. Our General Encyclopaedia contains the most noble qualities, such as faith, honesty, religion, kindness, honor, and modesty, which are in line with the spirit, way of life and traditions of our nation. The Constitution, as a symbol of our national statehood, serves to glorify the dignity of the individual and to ensure the inviolability of his or her legitimate interests. The principles enshrined in our encyclopedia are aimed at making everyone feel truly happy, peaceful and prosperous. Therefore, Allah glorified the human race and bestowed innumerable blessings on it. He attributed the qualities that he did not give to other creatures to man. Representatives of various religions living in our country, including the Muslims of our country, widely enjoy the rights and freedoms enshrined in our Constitution. In particular, this

document guarantees freedom of conscience and religion. According to Islamic teachings, religion is a set of divine instructions and practices that make a person believe in his will. Islam does not allow anyone to be forced into a religion or to impose their beliefs against the will of others. God created human beings and commanded them to live in peace, harmony and harmony. Allaah says in the Qur'aan:

“Verily, Allâh enjoins justice, good deeds, and the doing of good to one's relatives, and forbids corruption, evil, and oppression. He admonishes you that you may take heed. ”(Surat an-Nahl, 90)

Social justice plays an important role in ensuring that people in a society respect each other's rights and responsibilities and live by certain rules. In Islam, the rights and responsibilities of everyone in society, regardless of their nationality or creed, are clearly defined. There are 16 officially registered religious denominations in the country. More than 130 nationalities and ethnic groups live in peace and harmony. Ensuring cooperation and friendly relations between people of different religions and nationalities, ensuring that they work together for the development of the country is, first of all, the result of prudent policy pursued in Uzbekistan. But, unfortunately, the events in the world are trying to spread intolerance, enmity and hatred between different religions, thereby turning peaceful countries into unstable places. And we will have to live in tolerance with all the nations and religions that live in our country.

The rights to education, employment, medical treatment, belief, and property are also guaranteed in our religion. In our encyclopedia, these rights are guaranteed by special articles. Our religion also states that everyone in society has a duty and responsibility to the society in which he or she lives, to everyone in it, and to his or her homeland. It is said in the Qur'an:

“Worship Allah and do not associate anything with Him. And do good to the parents! Also, relatives, orphans, the poor, a neighbor, a neighbor, a stranger, your companion, a traveler, and your dependents! Indeed, Allah does not like those who are arrogant and boastful. ”(Surat an-Nisa ', 39)

From the content of the above verses and hadiths, it is clear that the laws are very important in human society. Indeed, just laws are the foundation of peace in the country, the well-being of the people, and the prosperity of this world and the hereafter.

What are the main aspects of the reforms in this area?

- You talked about the last five years. During these years of our national development, we have lived in a period of intense reforms. Under the

leadership of our President, historical changes have taken place. We have begun to achieve our great goals of building a new Uzbekistan, realizing the long-held dreams of our people, raising human rights to the highest level, finding solutions to existing problems. When justice is administered by a truly independent judiciary, human dignity, justice and the rule of law prevail. In this sense, ensuring the true independence of the judiciary is an important condition for building a democratic state governed by the rule of law and a strong civil society. When it comes to this, the initiatives put forward by the President in his speech at the ceremony dedicated to the 24th anniversary of the adoption of our Constitution are remembered. “Ensuring the inevitability of constitutional norms on the independence of the judiciary and the inevitability of liability for interference in the administration of justice is an important guarantee of achieving our goals. It is time to improve the quality of court proceedings, in particular, to prevent disturbances in civil cases, to put an end to the practice of making multiple decisions in the court of the same instance,” the President said.

In the recent past, comprehensive measures have been taken to ensure the true independence of the judiciary and to radically improve the judicial system. First of all, the reforms based on the Action Strategy have laid the groundwork for ensuring the true independence of the judiciary and increasing the role and importance of the courts in protecting the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of citizens. In the last 5 years, more than 50 laws, decrees and resolutions have been adopted on priority issues in this area. The normative legal acts of the judiciary have been updated in accordance with the reforms.

In particular, three new codes were adopted, and a number of other codes were significantly amended. New laws “On Courts”, “On the Supreme Council of Judges of the Republic of Uzbekistan” and “On the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan” were adopted. On this legal basis, the judicial system has been radically improved. Reforms aimed at further reforming the judiciary serve, first of all, to ensure the true independence of the judiciary, to protect human rights and freedoms, and the legitimate interests of individuals. The results are illustrated by institutional reforms aimed at improving the structure of the judiciary in line with modern requirements, ensuring the openness and transparency of the judiciary, and strengthening human rights protection.

In particular, on the initiative of the President five years ago to extend the term of office of judges, to form a highly qualified judiciary capable of

making fair decisions in court, new procedures have been introduced for the selection and appointment of candidates for judicial positions.

The first five-year, then ten-year, and then indefinite terms of office were important in ensuring that the judiciary was independent and subject only to the law. At the same time, the re-election or appointment of judges to the next term, as well as the election or appointment for a term of ten years or even indefinitely, after exemplary performance of their duties, also serves as a source of incentives. The court funding system has been brought into line with international standards. In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 13, 2021 "On measures to radically improve the system of financing the activities of the judiciary", salaries and bonuses of judges and court staff are fully funded from the state budget. The social protection of judges has been strengthened. This, of course, is an important guarantee of judicial independence.

Ensuring genuine independence of judges and increasing the effectiveness of preventing corruption in the judiciary is also important. Therefore, in accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 7, 2020 "On measures to ensure genuine independence of judges and increase the effectiveness of prevention of corruption in the judiciary" in order to prevent any interference in the activities of judges:

first, the Chairman of the Council submits a report to the prosecutor's office on cases of violation of the inviolability of judges and interference in the administration of justice;

second, the procedure for summoning judges for questioning as witnesses or suspects with the consent of the relevant qualification commissions was established.

Initially, the Supreme Court and the Supreme Economic Court merged into the Supreme Court, the only supreme body of the judiciary in civil, criminal, administrative, and economic proceedings, in order to establish a single judicial practice. In this regard, regional courts of general jurisdiction have been established on the basis of regional and equivalent civil, criminal and economic courts, while maintaining strict specialization of judges. It should be noted that this practice serves to eliminate unnecessary bureaucratic barriers to judicial protection, to bring the current structure of the judiciary in line with modern requirements and international standards.

- Extensive work has been done to ensure reliable protection of the rights and freedoms of citizens. Today, when it comes to the protection of

citizens' rights and freedoms, we have the opportunity to analyze these and other reforms. Therefore, please tell us in detail about the content of effective measures in this regard.

— This is a very important reform that our people have been waiting for for many years. The main task of the courts is to ensure reliable protection of the rights and freedoms of citizens through the administration of justice. Comprehensive measures have been taken in this direction in the past. In particular, for the first time, administrative courts have been established to guarantee the right of citizens to appeal against decisions of government agencies and illegal actions or omissions of their officials. 990 applications were considered, of which 44,388 or 65% were satisfied. 5,478 decisions of governors were declared invalid, and the violated rights of citizens and legal entities were restored.

Another important reform of human rights has been the expansion of the Habeas Corps, the liberalization of criminal penalties, and the strengthening of guarantees of the rights and freedoms of citizens in the judicial process. In particular, the institute of remanding a criminal case for further investigation was abolished. Imprisonment has been abolished, alternatives to non-custodial alternatives have been expanded, and the institution of evidence has been radically improved. This, in turn, led to a thorough examination of all aspects of the case by the court and an objective assessment of the evidence, resulting in an increase in acquittals. In particular, 3,513 people have been acquitted in the past five years, and 743 in the first nine months of 2021 alone. In addition, 18,026 people were released from the courtroom, and 33,515 citizens were acquitted or amended on unfounded charges.

At first glance, these figures may seem like simple numbers. But if we imagine that so many unjustly accused people will return to their families and be released, we will have a clear idea of how the results of the reforms will be reflected in the fate of an ordinary person. All this is, without a doubt, a clear result of reforms in the judiciary. After all, freedom is the greatest blessing for man. Another important reform in this regard is the improvement of the institution of judicial review in order to ensure reliable protection of human rights. It should be noted that while in 2017, court decisions were reconsidered in 7 courts, the number of these instances has been reduced to 3 in the last three years. What does it mean to reduce the number of courts? This, of course, means that the infringed right can be effectively restored in a short period of time without unnecessary hassle and expense. Therefore, in accordance with international standards, a three-tier judicial

system was created: the first instance (district (city) courts, regional courts for certain categories of complex cases), the appellate instance (regional courts) and the cassation instance (Supreme Court). The principle of "court - one instance" was introduced. The oversight body, which has been challenged by international organizations and experts, has been completely abolished. It should be noted that the introduction of the principle of "one court - one instance" increases the level of access to justice for citizens. In order to ensure the principle of adversarial proceedings and equality of arms in the trial, the status of the cassation appeal filed by the defendant, the victim and their representatives was equated with the prosecutor's protest. In particular, the resumption of proceedings in criminal proceedings on the basis of newly discovered facts has now been granted only to other participants in the criminal proceedings, such as the convicted person, the acquitted person, their defense counsel and legal representatives, the victim and his representative. They had the right to petition the court to initiate proceedings on the basis of newly discovered facts.

- The action strategy also provided for the improvement of administrative, criminal, civil and economic legislation. What is the system in this process in Uzbekistan today?

- As you rightly pointed out, the Action Strategy identified four important aspects in this regard.

The first is the improvement and liberalization of criminal and criminal procedure legislation, the decriminalization of certain criminal acts, the humanization of criminal penalties and the order of their execution.

The second is to improve the efficiency and quality of justice, to improve the procedural framework of administrative, criminal, civil and economic proceedings.

Third is the improvement of criminal, civil and economic proceedings, and the reduction of duplicative powers and instances.

Fourth, the introduction of modern forms and methods of electronic judicial and enforcement proceedings.

In order to achieve these goals, first of all, the new Civil Procedure Code, the Economic Procedure Code and the Code of Administrative Procedure were adopted. They improved the procedural procedures in accordance with international standards, with an in-depth analysis of law enforcement practices, based on best international practices, and introduced new rules for the effective protection of the rights and legitimate interests of citizens and businesses. Norms related to the participation of the prosecutor in civil and economic cases have been brought into line with

international standards. It was established that the prosecutor could participate only in cases provided for by law or on the basis of his own claim, and that he had the right to request a case from the court to resolve the issue of cassation if there were appeals from the parties to the case. The Law on Mediation was adopted. It defines the basic concepts, goals, objectives and mechanisms of pre-trial civil and economic dispute resolution. New judicial institutions have been introduced and existing ones have been improved. In particular, the institution of conciliation in criminal proceedings has been expanded to include all instances. In criminal cases - preliminary hearings, in civil and economic courts - pre-trial hearings, simplified proceedings, mediation institutions were introduced. The institution of remanding a criminal case for further investigation was abolished by the court by introducing mechanisms to supplement the incompleteness of the investigation during the trial. In particular, the institute of remanding a criminal case for further investigation was abolished. Imprisonment was abolished, alternatives to non-custodial punishment were expanded, and the institution of evidence-based assessment was radically improved. Measures have been taken to liberalize criminal penalties for juveniles and to strengthen their legal protection in the conduct of proceedings. The law provides for the application of a law that excludes criminality, mitigates punishment, or otherwise improves an individual's condition. The effective time limits for the completion and removal of a conviction have been shortened. In connection with the reconciliation, the institute of exemption from criminal liability was expanded. The penalty of "compulsory community service" was introduced to strengthen educational interventions through involvement in community service. Some economic crimes that did not pose a significant social risk, did not conform to the principles of market relations, and hindered the development of entrepreneurship and economic turnover were decriminalized. The institute of "first hearing" was introduced in the process of appointing a criminal case to court. The Concept of Improving the Criminal and Criminal Procedure Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan was approved, which provides for increasing the transparency and efficiency of human rights and freedoms, the state of economic development, modern requirements, international standards, as well as the widespread use of information and communication technologies.

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